

Effect of phosphorus with and without zinc on wetland rice

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Data from the 1981 and 1982 dry season (DS), Long-Term Soil Fertility Trials at Lanrang Substation showed that application of Zn significantly decreased rice grain yields. Responses to phosphorus also were observed. We designed an experiment in the 1984-85 DS (Nov-Feb) to determine yield response of rice to different P rates, with and without Zn.

The clay loam soil had pH 5.9 (slightly acidic); 2.6% organic matter content (low); 9 ppm available P (medium); 13.8, 8.8, 0.8 meq exchangeable Ca, Mg, K/100 g soil (adequate).

P, N, and K were applied in the form

Response of IR54 to P with and without Zn. Lanrang, Indonesia, 1984-85 DS.

Treatment	Grain yield ^a	Straw yield
	(t/ha) at 14% moisture	(t/ha) (sun-dried)
Control	4.7	4.7
13 kg P	6.0	5.3
13 kg P + 5 kg ZnO	5.8	5.4
26 kg P	6.0	5.4
26 kg P + 5 kg ZnO	6.0	5.5
40 kg P	5.9	5.8
40 kg P + 5 kg ZnO	5.8	5.6
53 kg P	6.0	5.2
53 kg P + 5 kg ZnO	5.8	5.4
66 kg P	5.2	5.5
66 kg P + 5 kg ZnO	5.9	5.5
0 P + 100 kg N + 50 kg K + 5 kg ZnO	5.7	5.6
LSD (0.05)	0.7	0.8
(0.01)	0.8	0.9
CV (%)	9.5	8.4

^aBased on 25 hills free of rat damage (harvestable area = 4 m²).

of TSP, urea, and KCl, respectively; 100 kg N/ha and 50 kg P/ha were applied as basal. Treatments were arranged in a randomized complete block design with four replications (see table).

ZnO at 5 kg/ha with P rates ranging

from 13 kg P to 66 kg P/ha in 13-kg P increments did not significantly affect grain and straw yields of IR54. There were no significant differences between P with and without Zn. And there was no response to phosphorus. □

Response of spring rice to fertilizer practices in rice - rapeseed rotation

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Spring rice, the principal crop in the midhills of U.P., is sown under rainfed conditions in Mar and harvested in Sep. A short-duration (Oct-Feb) rapeseed (*Brassica campestris* L. var. *toria*) was found to fit the intervening period best. But yields are low because farmers use very low amounts of chemical fertilizers (4-5 kg/ha). Farmyard manure (FYM) is the principal source of plant nutrients.

We studied the response of spring rice to N and FYM and the residual effect on a succeeding rapeseed crop at Hawalbagh, Almora (1,250 m above mean sea level, average annual rainfall 1,027.3 mm) for 3 yr (1983-86).

The soil was sandy loam (pH 6.2, 0.43% organic C, CEC 22 meq/100 g,

Effect of N and FYM applied to spring rice on grain yield of spring rice and rapeseed. Almora, India, 1983-86.

Manurial treatment		Yield (t/ha)							
		1983-84		1984-85		1985-86		Mean	
N rate (kg/ha)	FYM (t/ha)	Rice	Rapeseed	Rice	Rapeseed	Rice	Rapeseed	Rice	Rapeseed
0	0	1.43	0.22	1.41	0.22	0.79	0.30	1.21	0.24
0	10	1.72	0.31	1.81	0.32	1.66	0.51	1.73	0.38
0	20	1.91	0.37	2.07	0.43	1.93	0.61	1.97	0.47
20	0	1.50	0.19	1.60	0.22	0.95	0.32	1.35	0.24
20	10	1.81	0.38	1.91	0.33	1.77	0.53	1.83	0.41
20	20	2.02	0.37	2.26	0.44	2.28	0.62	2.19	0.48
LSD (0.05) N		0.10	ns	0.15	ns	0.15	ns		
FYM		0.16	0.06	0.13	0.08	0.15	0.03		
N×FYM		ns	ns	ns	ns	ns	ns		

22.7 kg available P (Bray's)/ha, 229.6 kg available K/ha). Two levels of N (0 and 20 kg N/ha) and three levels of FYM (0, 10, and 20 t/ha) were applied only to spring rice, in a factorial randomized block design with three replications. FYM applied the first yr had 0.65% N, 0.23% P, 0.60% K, and 18.8% moisture content; in the second yr, it had 0.61% N, 0.27% P, 0.58% K, and 16.7%

moisture content; and in the third year it had 0.56% N, 0.21% P, 0.65% K, and 15.5% moisture content. Rice variety VL 206 was seeded the second half of Mar and harvested the middle of Sep. Rapeseed variety T9 was planted the beginning of Oct and harvested in the second half of Feb.

Rice yield increased by 0.14 t/ha with 20 kg N/ha (see table). Yield increases